

C L I M A T E S C A L E

Uncertainties in wind resource projections and the economics of wind farm portfolios

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Uncertainties in wind resource projections

Overview

- CMIP6 (more than 20 models)
- Surface wind and wind speed at 100m, 200m
- Data at native model levels
- Vertical interpolation to target heights (see Hahman et al., 2022)
- Land use impact: LUH2, land use forcing for CMIP6
- Comparison of surface wind and wind speed at hub height from climate models
- Investigate the impact of land use on uncertainty

Reducing uncertainty is key for wind resource projections

- Often, long-term trends in surface wind are relatively small
- Uncertainties in surface wind changes do not depend too much on the specific scenario
- But, ensemble spread of projected changes can be relatively large

Projected Changes of Surface Wind in Europe

- CMIP6 surface wind changes relative to 2006 - 2025
- 21 models
- Ensemble mean

A driver of trends: land use changes

- Land use changes, especially vegetation, has been identified as a major contributor to wind speed changes over land (see, e.g., Wohland et al., 2024)
- Shown are increase/decreases of the percentage of primary and secondary land (forested and low vegetation)

A driver of trends: land use changes

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Projected Changes of Wind Resource at hub height

- Wind at hub height (200m) shows reduced changes in many land use impacted areas over land
- Reduce the impact of land use changes on wind by using wind output from the atmosphere component at higher, more relevant heights

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Wind speed changes and uncertainty at different heights

- Many hotspot areas show weaker trends at greater heights
- Reduced ensemble spread at higher levels (model uncertainty)

Impact of land use on wind speed depends on complexity of climate models (surface component).

Model uncertainty increases ensemble spread near surface

Comparing the uncertainty

Uncertainty ratio

- Definition: 90% ensemble range of changes for surface wind speed divided by hub height wind ensemble range
- >1 surface wind speed ensemble spread is larger than for hub height
- <1 surface wind speed is less uncertain
- =1 both are the same

Comparing the uncertainty

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Some Conclusions

Uncertainties for wind climate projections can be relatively large when compared to long-term trends

Native model level data for hub height wind speed

- is less prone to be driven by land use changes
- can reduce ensemble spread and uncertainty

From wind uncertainty to financial impacts

PHYSICAL CLIMATE RISK ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK — IIGCC PCRAM 2.0

This presentation focuses on Step 2 —
assessing materiality for chronic hazards at a North Denmark wind farm site.

CHRONIC HAZARDS — modelled in this use case

Hazard	Direct impact	KPI
Changing wind patterns	Energy → revenue	LCOE · IRR
Temperature derating	Energy → revenue	LCOE · IRR
Icing losses	Energy → revenue	LCOE · IRR
Sea level rise, other...	Site-specific	TBD

ACUTE HAZARDS — not modelled here

Hazard	Direct	Indirect
Heat stress	OPEX (productivity)	—
Flooding	CAPEX · insurance	OPEX · continuity
Wildfires	CAPEX · insurance	OPEX · continuity
Extreme winds / TCs	CAPEX · insurance	OPEX · continuity
Landslides · subsidence...	Site-specific	TBD

This presentation focuses on Step 2 — assessing materiality for chronic hazards at a North Denmark wind farm site.

Objectives

Analyse if projected changes in wind patterns, temperature and icing losses are material for a project.
Use LCOE, CVar and IRR as KPIs to identify materiality.

Three KPIs are used to estimate if climate change impacts are material to the project

COST METRIC

Levelised Cost of Energy
(LCOE)

$$LCOE = \frac{NPV_{costs}}{NPE} = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^{t=N} \frac{CAPEX_t + OPEX_t}{(1+d)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^{t=N} \frac{GENERATION_t}{(1+d)^t}}$$

d = discount rate, related to WACC

RETURN METRIC

Internal Rate of Return
(IRR)

The discount rate at which the net present value of the project equals zero — the project's actual annualised return.

$$NPV_{project} = NPV_{revenues} - NPV_{costs} = 0$$

$$NPV_{revenues} = \sum_{t=1}^{t=N} \frac{GENERATION_t \times PRICE_t}{(1+IRR)^t}$$

RISK METRIC

Climate Value at Risk
(CVaR)

The financial loss attributable to climate change — the difference in NPV between a present-climate and future-climate scenario.

$$CVaR = NPV_{present} - NPV_{CC}$$

CC = climate change scenario

Positive CVaR → climate change reduces project value

TURBINE & FINANCIAL PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Turbine capacity	3.55 MW
Hub height	150 m
CAPEX	1.6 M €/MW
OPEX	41.5 K €/MW/yr
Insurance	3.5 K €/MW/yr
Connection charges	5.0 K €/MW/yr
Project lifetime	25 years
Discount rate	7%

Source: Fraunhofer ISE, Levelized Cost of Electricity Renewable Energy Technologies (July 2024)

ENERGY ADJUSTMENTS

Factor	Condition
Temperature derating	Temperate climates
Icing losses	temp < 0°C RH > 80% wind > 3 m/s
Availability	98%
Degradation rate	0.5% / year

POWER CURVE

Threshold	Value
Cut-in wind speed	3 m/s
Rated wind speed	12 m/s
Cut-out wind speed	25 m/s

POWER CURVE (3.55 MW turbine)

Climate drives through exactly three variables:

wind speed · temperature · relative humidity — all other parameters are held fixed across baseline and projection periods.

Baseline KPIs

Use case: Site North Denmark

DATA SOURCE

Vortex hourly time series: wind speed, temperature, relative humidity at hub height

Period: 2005 – 2024

BASELINE KPIs

Metric	Value
Average annual energy	12.5 GWh
P50 annual energy	12.7 GWh
P10 annual energy	10.9 GWh
Capacity factor	0.40
LCOE	54.5 €/MWh
Annual revenue	819,674 €
Baseline electricity price *	65.5 €/MWh

* Estimated assuming the discount rate equals the equity IRR ≈ 10%

○ Operating Windfarms

Climate projections — North Denmark

SSP5-8.5 · CMIP6 downscaled ensemble · hub height 150 m

mean annual wind

mean annual temperature

Vortex (WRF-ERA5) 3km

Climate Scale ENERGY+ (CMIP6 calibrated with Vortex)

- ensemble median
- grey: climate models

Energy projections — what drives the change?

SSP5-8.5 · distribution across CMIP6 models · North Denmark

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SSP5-8.5 · distribution across CMIP6 models · North Denmark

GWh/year

P50 of annual Energy distribution

%

Energy Losses due to Icing

Energy projections — what drives the change?

SSP5-8.5 · distribution across CMIP6 models · North Denmark

GWh/year

P50 of annual Energy distribution

%

Energy Losses due to temperature

Financial Impacts

Change in LCOE wrt Baseline

CVar: change in NPV (baseline - future)

What changes to LCOE are material?

- Is a an increase in LCOE (or a decrease in energy P50) of ~3% material?
 - +3% in LCOE is equivalent to, if energy is kept fixed, an increase in IRR of -.5%
- Would that be material to the project?

LCOE - materiality and resilience

If energy is projected to decrease, can adaptation measures will be implemented that will keep LCOE equal or smaller than the baseline LCOE?

Assuming

- CC impact on energy: 3% decrease in energy P50, or equivalently, 3% increase in LCOE.
- all other parameters are kept fixed

adaptation measures will reverse the impact on LCOE only in the green area.

E.g. an adaptation measure that costs ~1% of CAPEX to implement, will only be effective if it increases the energy by 4% or more (see vertical arrow in graph).

Wind resource:

No strong trend in wind speeds at hub height across the CMIP6 ensemble for this site.
Model uncertainty dominates through 2084.

Icing and temperature

Warming effects impact through reductions in losses due to icing. Temperature derating is very small through 2084.

Economics:

Impacts on LCOE and CVar are modest.

Impact of a change in energy $\sim 3\%$ in LCOE is equivalent to a change in 0.5% in IRR \rightarrow within stress testing of financial model?

Resilience

For impacts on resource/energy generation, and under the assumption of the use case, any adaptation measure that raises CAPEX or OPEX must result in enough extra energy generated to compensate for increased expenditure - is this possible?

The analysis focused on chronic impacts only does not seem to leave room for building in resilience.

Acute hazards (extreme wind, flooding, wildfires) are not captured in this simplified model. Including them might substantially change the resilience picture.

When climate change impacts on wind farm economics are comparable in magnitude to standard financial parameters uncertainty:

should climate change be modelled as a widening of the uncertainty, rather than a shift in the P50 estimate?

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$$\text{WACC} = (\text{Fraction financed by debt}) \times (\text{Cost of debt}) \times (1 - \text{Tax Rate}) + (\text{Fraction financed by equity}) \times (\text{Cost of equity}).$$

The WACC represents the discount rate that a company should use in conducting a discounted cash flow analysis of a given energy project. The reason is that the discount rate represents the opportunity cost of getting something in the future relative to getting something today. Since the WACC represents the average return for an energy project (remembering that that average is weighted across both debt and equity investors), it represents a kind of average opportunity cost for investment in a project.